

USE OF EDUCATIONAL FILMS IN BIOLOGY LESSONS

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Abstract. *Today, when there are more social demands in front of school, teaching biology should meet the requirements of socio-economic and scientific-technical development. At a time when great importance is attached to the practical direction in teaching biology, it is important for students to be able to connect biological phenomena with agriculture, biotechnology, environmental protection and other fields, and be able to apply them in life. It is important to use various educational tools to develop knowledge, skills and abilities in biology. Among them, visuality is important. The purpose of writing this article is to shed light on the effective methods of using educational films in biology classes today in the era of advanced science and information technology. In the classes, we aimed to make films not just a process of showing, but a process that creates a basis for learning, research, reflection, and practical application.*

Keywords: *video film, visual aids, educational material, physiological process, acquisition, comparison, activation, scientific material, repetition, generalization, didactic cards, announcer's explanation.*

INTRODUCTION

In the period when the material and technical base of educational institutions is improving day by day, showing educational films during the lesson is widely used in educational institutions. They have the importance of expanding and strengthening students' knowledge, worldview, and increasing their interest in science. In addition, they facilitate teacher's work, help in easy learning of educational material. During the screening of the film, a scene is created in the mind of the students that shows the life of nature, full of dynamics, or a part of it, and the voice of the announcer explains it. Video films, which are part of the technical means of education, help to demonstrate the educational material, its systematic delivery, help students understand and remember the educational material well.

But in order to learn the educational material in the film, it cannot be simply shown, in which case it is necessary to follow certain rules depending on the content and complexity of the film. In this article, we have tried to give the necessary recommendations to increase the efficiency of learning of scientific material in films, strengthen acceptance, and strengthen knowledge.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

According to the content and structure of the films, the character of the lecture text, the time and method of inclusion in the educational process, they are divided into visual or research-activating films.

Experiences obtained in the film help to express the sequence of experiences, their conditions, processes, to see processes that cannot be implemented in institutional conditions, to understand processes that are not visible to the naked eye.

Multiplications are important in elucidating the dynamics of physiological processes. For example, the fight against infection by leukocytes is explained in an easy and convenient way

when multiplying films are used to explain the inflammatory process. Similarly, the circulation of blood in the circulatory system, the successive contraction of the ventricles and chambers during the heartbeat are presented to the students in a simple and understandable way.

Films about plants and animals are distinguished by their diversity and vitality. For example, films about the way of life of animals, their behavior and diversity provide more information in other visual media.

The effect of the films representing the characteristic properties of the object (size, hardness, humidity, tension, volume, etc.) will not be very high, even if explained in advance. In this case, working with natural objects or mock-ups gives a higher result.

In the experiment, it became clear that sometimes, after watching films with a clear plan, consistency and rich content, when the teacher asked a question, the students could not give a complete answer. When the students were asked what they had trouble answering, they answered that the film was interesting, but it was shown too quickly, and they did not remember anything.

How to strengthen the reception of information in the film, strengthen knowledge?

Before showing the films intended to provide scientific material, the teacher must first explain the topic, and to provide additional information on the topic and reinforce it, it can be interpreted by showing the film. It is useless to try to master it. For this purpose, re-showing some parts of the film after the film screening or commenting during the film screening will improve the learning process.

When students are tasked with recalling more information about the film before the film is shown, students are asked about the information they remember after the film is shown. The subject can be strengthened by asking questions about the parts that have not been remembered or ignored, or the film can be shown again by asking problematic questions. When it is repeated, emphasis is placed on the places that the students did not pay attention to before.

In the course of the lesson, students remember short, experimental films more than coherent, voluminous information. It was observed that materials reflecting life processes, for example, materials with a hygienic content, are remembered more.

In the first place are films that bring emotions to remember. For example, short films comparing the lungs of smokers and non-smokers, the effects of nicotine on the body, the effects of parasites on the body, mutations, and genetic diseases are well remembered by students.

But it was more difficult to remember them if the films showed tables, schemes, numerical comparisons, complex physiological processes. Additional explanations, visual aids, games and other technologies can be used for this.

The explanation of the film material is based on the content of the film. For films with new and complex material, the explanation should be conducted before the film screening. For example, "Organ of hearing", "Organ of vision", "Mendel's laws", etc. If the film is shown before the explanation, the students will not be able to learn the physiology of the organs without fully understanding the anatomical structure.

Films such as "Circulation", "Structure and function of the respiratory organs", "Structure and function of the heart", "The influence of man on nature" are well absorbed by students before and after the explanation, because the students will have prior knowledge about the topics.

It will give a good result if the explanatory work in mastering such topics as "Animal Behavior", "Animal Diversity", "Importance of Plants", "The Effect of Temperature on Living Organisms" is carried out after the film screening.

In order to absorb the information in the film more effectively, we need to plan the students' learning activities. For this purpose, it would be appropriate if they were given an assignment suitable for the topic and the film. The difficulty in creating the task is that all the information is given in the text of the announcer in the film. Therefore, the student's learning will be passive. The skill of the teacher is to choose the right type of task to activate the passive form. The assignment should include comparisons, generalizations, causality, and focus on key frames.

For example, before the screening of the film on "Blood Circulation", students can be given the following tasks:

1. Pay attention to the starting and ending points of each circulatory circle. How are blood circulation circles defined?
2. In which blood vessels of the large and small circulatory circles does arterial blood flow and in which venous blood flows?
3. What is the blood pressure in veins, arteries and capillaries of large blood circulation circles?
4. How is a person's blood pressure measured?
5. What experience is shown in the film? What does it prove?
6. What important conclusions have you drawn for your health?

In some cases, didactic cards are created for films. They may include the plan of the film, a short annotation of some shots, and questions asked to understand the material. The cards can sometimes be read and discussed before the film, and sometimes after, if the film is not complicated.

For example, we can use the following card for the film "Respiratory Hygiene".

Table 1

Image content	Questions to be answered in the film
Pine grove. By the sea	Why is it easy to breathe in the forest and on the seashore?
The process of determining the process of pollination	Is there a lot of dust in the forest?
Release of phytoncides by trees	What are phytoncides?
Checking the air in the classroom	How is the weather in the classroom?
Classroom cleaning	What is the importance of cleaning with a damp cloth?
Air movement in room ventilation	What should you pay attention to when ventilating the room?
The lungs of a smoker and a non-smoker	Negative effects of smoking on health?
Diseases of respiratory organs.	What to do to prevent diseases?

The use of such cards enhances the effect of receiving information in the film. Pupils can restore frames from the film in memory on a didactic card and solve various interesting and problematic problems.

Need an explanation during a movie screening?

There is no single answer to this question. In some films, the announcer gives complete and detailed information. There is no need for the teacher to give information even during breaks. But not all classes can bear the same psychological load, and sometimes the teacher helps to

understand with the help of bites if necessary. Or, if necessary, the film can be stopped and students can be asked questions during the screening for different prepared classes.

In some cases, the announcer's comment can be turned off and the teacher himself can comment. In some lessons, when we offered the students to turn off the sound and comment on the film after the film was shown, the students were able to do it.

The effectiveness of learning the educational film is greatly increased when the film is shown in parts. In this case, firstly, the film material is given in small parts, secondly, active learning of the previous part helps to learn the next part, and thirdly, students' answers are checked at once and errors are analyzed.

After the film screening, the assimilation of the film material is checked, and for deeper assimilation of knowledge, the parts that the students did not understand are explained with the help of tables, color exhibits, pictures drawn on the board, and models. During the discussion after the film screening, attention will be paid to the information known to the students and new to them.

For example, in the study of the topic "Structure and function of the kidneys", if the film is shown after explaining the topic with the help of models, color exhibits, it is not necessary to give instruction on the film, but in the final interview, the teacher primary and secondary should monitor absorption by asking questions about the process of urine formation, filtration, reabsorption, and the structure of kidney nephrons.

CONCLUSION

It is important to use films in modern lessons in the era of the development of today's information technologies. In order to increase the efficiency of the lesson, it is important to effectively use biofilms to ensure the vitality of the topic in biology lessons.

Before or after the use of biofilms, it is necessary to use didactic cards, instructions, questions and answers, conversation, and explanations correctly, based on the content, for better learning of the educational material in them. For this, it is appropriate to create a lesson plan taking into account the level of preparation of the class, the psychological state, and the level of complexity of the subject.

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